

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL CAPITAL IN HUMAN-SOCIETY- STATE RELATIONS.

Nadir Ibrahimovich Uktamov

Namangan State University
foundation doctoral student

E-mail: nadiruktamov2@gmail.com
+998958222932

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987212>

Abstract: Social capital is an important factor in human-society-state relations. It has been revealed that social capital serves as an important tool in solving issues related to social relations, people's relations with each other, state and society. Social capital includes people's cooperation, mutual trust, and support. This is aimed at the establishment of cooperation, freedom, justice, mutual respect and determination in society.

Key words: Society, state, Human, Social capital, solidarity, trust, civil society, development, democracy.

In the construction of New Uzbekistan and the creation of a modern Uzbek society in our country, increasing the social capital factor and aiming for global development along the way, fundamentally changing the economic-political, spiritual-educational spheres, thereby creating the basis of an informed society creation is today's main task. In this way, it is difficult to achieve any progress without improving the relations between people, society and the state.

Based on this, we all know very well that today's sustainable development of humanity requires new theories and concepts in order to consciously work in the processes of globalization. One of these concepts is undoubtedly social capital. About this concept in the last periods of the last century has already become the center of attention of all researchers conducting scientific research. Economists, sociologists, philosophers and politicians have widely discussed social capital . Therefore, this term is one of the widespread trends of modern society .

First, to explain the important role of social capital in society, we need to understand social capital itself. Social capital consists of knowledge, experience, general skills, communication and cooperation acquired in the interaction of people, groups and social organizations. It serves as an important tool in the development of society's mutual trust, support, freedom, justice, human rights, innovation, social progress and democracy.

Social capital serves as a conceptual basis of special importance in human-society-state relations. This includes cooperation of people with society, mastering of mutual trust and support, development of society, increase of innovation and production power, active participation of citizens in processes related to state policy, provision of social stability and prospects. As the leader of our country noted, "...the effect of the economic reforms and social changes we are implementing is measured, first of all, by the extent to which they affect the material condition and well-being of the population, the level and quality of life " and a high level of social capital has a great impact on the overall development and stability of society [1].

A high level of social capital creates many positive behaviors in society. The importance of social capital in human-society-state relations can be described below:

First of all. Development of society: Social capital is of great importance in the development of society. Its high level allows innovation, social progress and development of spirituality. Social capital is acquired through the acquired experience, knowledge and skills of participants in society in many areas, and therefore serves as the main tool for better conveying society's attitude to moral values to future generations.

Secondly. Social engagement: Social capital fosters mutual understanding and support between people. This leads to the establishment of freedom, justice and determination in society. A high level of social capital shows that the citizens in the society are not indifferent to the relations taking place in every field.

Thirdly. Innovation and Productivity Enhancement: Social capital enables innovation and productivity enhancement. Many people in society stimulate new ideas and creativity with their acquired knowledge and experience. A high level of social capital increases the development of ideas and innovations in society.

Fourthly. Social stability and prospects: Social capital provides social stability and prospects in a society. The knowledge and experience acquired by a single person serves the overall development of society. Social capital increases trust, respect, support and fairness between people in society, which leads to the development of a stable and resilient society.

Social capital is one of the important aspects in the development of society. Through the role of social capital in the structure of the state, many relationships can be positively organized. Social capital, by working together with state and community organizations, forms the structure of the state,

stimulates its activity and increases change. Today, social capital is an important part of the state structure's strategies aimed at increasing participation and community development by increasing social activity and strengthening public control in ensuring the relations of citizens in the state structure. In particular, low civic activity, weak ties between citizens, which reduces the stock of social capital of society [3]. Through these strategies, countries seek to solve issues such as supporting the active citizenship position of the society, development of mutual communication and cooperation, protection of human rights, development of payment and tax systems, strengthening of social economy and others. In addition, the development of the economic sphere of the society is an important part of the social capital, the strategies of the state structure aimed at stimulating economic development. Through these strategies, they seek to stimulate innovations and investments in the state, economic sectors, develop the industrial and sector structure, increase business activity and strengthen production. Improving the material life of the state through social capital is the basis for reducing the number of unemployment in society, reducing the level of poverty of citizens, and determining the power of the state.

Also, the role of social capital in the state structure can be determined by specific organized indicators. Each country will have its own strategies for acquiring social capital and strengthening its position in society. According to Eric, an American political scientist, "High electoral processes in the state can lead to a high level of social capital provision. In today's highly competitive elections and campaigns, party leaders directly address voters through the media, increasing the role of party activists.[2] These strategies will depend on the country's politics, economic situation, culture and other areas. The role of social capital in the state structure is a strategic part of society aimed at supporting, developing and ensuring successful growth of its values. As a clear example of this, our country is fully developing through the "Strategy of Actions" for 2017-2021 and the "Strategy of Development" for 2022-2026.

The following ways are widely used to absorb social capital in the state structure:

First- Stimulation of education and socio-spiritual sphere: Social capital can be mastered by developing the state education system and improving its quality. This includes promoting reforms in the spiritual and educational fields, changes in the field of science and technology, ensuring support for education, strengthening educational resources and encouraging innovation.

Second - Improving Health and Healthy Lifestyles: Social capital can be harnessed by improving public health reforms. This consists in developing the infrastructure and services in the field of health care, ensuring health, strengthening the system of prevention and treatment of diseases, training professional doctors and increasing the average life expectancy, striving to maintain the health of the society.

Thirdly- Protection of social rights: One of the important parts of social capital appropriation of the state is the protection of social rights. This includes issues such as ensuring the justice system, building a legal environment, supporting human rights, eliminating gender inequalities, and ensuring tolerance with ethnic and cultural communities.

Summarizing the concept of social capital, we can see that the complexity and diversity of social capital's manifestations is one of the main reasons for the development of modern socio-philosophical aspects of theoretical traditions and production. So, the idea of social capital is the result of a long and complex evaluation of personal development. It is necessary to study the socio-philosophical interpretation of social capital and requires development through the mechanical connection between society. In the study of social capital, distribution, justification of its problems, the fundamentals of productivity and the development of systems of social relations are assumed. Based on these requirements, it was decided to define the factors of social capital development and reveal its external parts and possible manifestations. The proposed assessment of social capital includes its content.

List of references used:

1. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Эркин ва фаровон демократик Ўзбекистон давлатини биргаликда барпо этамиз. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2016. – Б. 21.
2. Райт Э. О. Что такое аналитический марксизм? // Вопросы экономики, 2007. № 9.
3. Putnam R. D. Bowling Alone: The Collapse and Revival of American Community. New York; Touchstone Books by Simon & Schuster, 2001. p.85
4. Sodirjonov M. M. Monitoring the issues of human capital research in ethnosocial processes and social trends //Social policy and social partnership. – 2021. – №. 6. – С. 6.

